

**Chemiluminescence blot
for Figure 1A**

**GAPDH NIR fluorescence
blot for Figure 1A**

**Chemiluminescence blot
for Figure 1B**

**GAPDH NIR fluorescence
blot for Figure 1B**

**Chemiluminescence blot
for Figure 7A**

**GAPDH NIR fluorescence
blot for Figure 7A**